

Observing and Analyzing Collaboration Skills Through the STAD (Student Teams Achievement Division) Cooperative Learning Model

Robinson R. Bobu¹, Suryo Widodo², Yuni Katminingsih³

^{1,2,3}Department of Mathematics Education, Faculty of Health and Science, Nusantara PGRI University, Kediri

ARTICLE INFO	ABSTRACT
Published Online: 23 June 2026	Many studies have been conducted to investigate the impact of collaboration skills. The findings of this study indicate that all learning groups achieved levels ranging from active to highly active, with relatively high levels of collaboration skill attainment. In general, the implementation of the STAD learning model was able to create a conducive and collaborative learning environment, as well as increase student engagement in group work. Furthermore, the implementation of the Student Teams Achievement Division (STAD) learning model had a positive impact on students' collaboration skills. This is demonstrated by the average collaborative skills score of 70.58%, which falls within the "active" category. Therefore, the STAD model can be considered as a learning alternative capable of supporting the development of students' collaborative skills in learning activities. Based on the observation results, the implementation of the <i>Student Teams Achievement Division</i> (STAD) learning model has proven effective in improving students' collaboration skills in mathematics learning. Improvements were observed in the aspects of active participation, cooperation, the ability to express ideas, and cooperation among group members, which fell into the "active" to "very active" categories.
Corresponding Author: Suryo Widodo	This indicates that the STAD model is effective in encouraging student engagement, strengthening positive interactions, and fostering collaborative learning.
KEYWORDS: learning model, STAD, collaboration, cooperative, skills.	

I. INTRODUCTION

Efforts to achieve quality education require a continuously optimized learning process (Mubarak, 2021). One of the main goals of education is to improve students' skills and learning outcomes. However, various challenges still arise in practice, such as students' difficulties in understanding learning materials and collaborating with peers (Ichiana et al., 2023). These conditions place teachers in a crucial role in determining instructional models capable of optimally fostering student engagement and active participation (Arum & Hanif, 2025).

Education in the 21st century no longer focuses solely on mastering learning content but also on strengthening critical thinking, communication skills, creativity, and collaboration (Nurhayati et al., 2025). Collaborative skills are a vital aspect because they equip students to adapt and compete in the face of global challenges. In the context of mathematics learning, collaboration plays a role in encouraging students to support

one another, exchange ideas, and work together to solve the problems they face (Pare & Sihotang, 2023).

However, classroom teaching practices are still largely dominated by conventional approaches that center on the teacher as the focal point of learning (Suryo Widodo et al., 2019). This situation leads students to tend to be passive, minimally engaged in discussions, and lacking motivation to collaborate, resulting in the underdevelopment of collaborative skills (Noperman, 2022).

One alternative that can be used to develop students' collaborative skills is the implementation of cooperative learning models (Wahyudi, 2024). Student Teams Achievement Division (STAD) is a form of cooperative learning that organizes students into small, heterogeneous groups to learn together and support one another (Aje, 2022). Through this model, interaction among students can be enhanced while fostering a sense of shared responsibility in achieving optimal learning outcomes.

“Observing and Analyzing Collaboration Skills Through the STAD (Student Teams Achievement Division) Cooperative Learning Model”

A number of previous studies have shown that the implementation of the STAD learning model is effective in improving students' social skills and learning outcomes. Research conducted by the found that the STAD model has a positive effect on students' mathematics learning outcomes, indicating that the use of the STAD model positively influences students' mathematics learning outcomes. Furthermore, the findings of this study also indicate that the implementation of STAD is capable of encouraging students' active engagement in discussion and group collaboration activities (Liu et al., 2025). Thus, these research findings reinforce the view that STAD-based learning can be used as an appropriate strategy for developing students' collaboration skills (Margalita et al., 2025).

This study was designed to empirically examine the effectiveness of implementing the STAD model in enhancing students' collaboration skills, given the lack of direct application and testing by previous researchers. Based on this discussion, it is deemed necessary to conduct research examining the influence of the STAD learning model on students' collaboration skills in mathematics learning (LIA, 2021).

Based on the entire discussion, the researcher assesses that an empirical study is needed on the application of the Student Teams Achievement Division (STAD) learning model on students' collaboration skills in mathematics learning. This study is expected not only to provide academic evidence regarding the effectiveness of the STAD model but also to contribute to the development of innovative, contextual mathematics learning strategies that align with the demands of 21st-century education

II. RESEARCH METHOD

This study employs a quantitative approach using a descriptive research design. Quantitative descriptive research aims to systematically and objectively describe students' collaborative activities within groups during mathematics instruction (Nirfayanti & Syamsuriyawati, 2024). This study does not aim to compare classes or test the effects of specific interventions but rather to describe the level of student engagement in collaborating with group members based on the observational data collected.

In this study, the researcher observed students' collaborative activities in mathematics lessons that applied the Student Teams Achievement Division (STAD) cooperative learning model. The study was conducted without a control group and without an experimental treatment (Abdurahman et al., 2024).

Data analysis is the process of systematically obtaining and organizing data collected from field surveys and documentation by categorizing the data, breaking it down into units, synthesizing it, arranging it into patterns, selecting what is important and what needs to be studied, and drawing conclusions so that the findings are easily understood by oneself or others (Darmawan et al., 2021). The fundamental

purpose of data analysis is to answer the research question and test the formulated hypothesis. The data were obtained from the results of the post-test on students' collaboration skills, both individually and in groups. Data analysis was conducted quantitatively using the following steps:

The observational data were analyzed using quantitative descriptive analysis with the following steps:

The observational data were analyzed using quantitative descriptive analysis with the following steps (ZISPITA, 2025):

Calculating students' collaboration skill scores per group

1. maximum student score:

$$SM = n \times m \times S_{maks}$$

2. Total score obtained:

$$P = \frac{SP_{total}}{SM} \times 100\%$$

3. Convert to a percentage

$$P = \frac{f}{N} \times 100\%$$

Note: P = percentage of collaboration skills

f = score obtained

N = maximum score

4. Calculating the mean for descriptive statistics:

$$\text{mean (average): } \bar{X} = \frac{\sum X}{n}$$

5. Categorizing students' collaboration activity percentages into the following categories:

- 81–100% = Very Active
- 61–80% = Active
- 41–60% = Fairly Active
- ≤40% = Not Very Active

The results of the data analysis are used to provide an overview of the level of student collaboration within groups.

III. RESULTS

Following the observation and pilot testing of students' collaboration skills, the assessment process was conducted based on observations of student activities during mathematics lessons that implemented the *Student Teams Achievement Division* (STAD) cooperative learning model (Wahyudi, 2024). The next step was to determine the components required for the assessment calculation process by utilizing the observation sheet as a research instrument.

The observation sheet was designed to include six indicators of collaborative skills, covering the number of agreement intervals among observers, the number of observation intervals, the percentage of indicator achievement, and the (MARIYAM, 2024) assessment categories.

Group 1

- a. **Calculation Results per Indicator**

1. Collaboration skills focused on the aspect of asking questions for 30 minutes

“Observing and Analyzing Collaboration Skills Through the STAD (Student Teams Achievement Division) Cooperative Learning Model”

Figure 4.1: Diagram of the questioning aspect

Based on the data on collaboration skills in the “asking questions” aspect over a 30-minute period, the highest score/percentage was achieved by Finza Agustina, who scored 100% and fell into the “Very Active” category. This level of activity indicates that Finza has a high level of curiosity, is not afraid to ask about things she does not yet understand, and is able to encourage interaction and communication within the group, making discussions more lively and focused.

2. Collaboration skills focused on the “responding” aspect over a 30-minute period

Figure 4.2: Diagram of the “Answering” Aspect

Based on observations of collaboration skills regarding the “responding” aspect over a 30-minute period, there was variation in students’ levels of activity when responding to questions or providing answers during the discussion. Helmy Achmad demonstrated the highest achievement with a 100% response rate and was categorized as “very active.” Furthermore, Finza Agustina was also classified as “very active” with an 87.5% response rate, indicating that she was quite dominant in providing responses and helped facilitate smooth communication within the group.

3. Collaboration skills focused on the aspect of active participation over a 30-minute period

Figure 4.3: Diagram of active participation

Based on the observation results regarding active participation over 30 minutes, it can be seen that the majority of students demonstrated excellent engagement in group collaboration activities. Handhika Putra P, Jonathan Chrise, and Helmy Achmad achieved a 100% participation rate, falling into the “very active” category. This indicates that all three were fully engaged in the discussion process, such as by sharing their opinions, responding to peers, and taking on roles.

4. Collaboration Skills Focused on the Aspect of Working Together for 30 Minutes

Figure 4.4: Diagram of the “Working Together” Aspect

Based on the results of the observation of collaboration skills regarding the aspect of working together for 30 minutes, it is evident that students’ abilities to establish group cooperation varied from one individual to another. Handhika Putra P achieved the highest percentage—100%—in the “very active” category, indicating that he was highly consistent throughout the activity. Next, Jonathan Chrise achieved a percentage of 85.71% and fell into the “active” category, indicating that he was quite cooperative and able to contribute to group work.

5. Collaboration skills focused on the aspect of contributing ideas over a 30-minute period.

Figure 4.5: Diagram of the “generating ideas” aspect

Based on the observation results regarding the “idea generation” aspect over 30 minutes, it is evident that students’ abilities to contribute ideas during group discussions still vary. Helmy Achmad achieved the highest percentage—100%—in the “very active” category, indicating that he was highly dominant in presenting ideas, making suggestions, and helping the group find solutions or steps to resolve problems.

“Observing and Analyzing Collaboration Skills Through the STAD (Student Teams Achievement Division) Cooperative Learning Model”

6. Collaboration skills focused on the aspect of cooperation among members for 30 minutes

Figure 4.6: Diagram of the aspect of cooperation among group members

2. Collaboration skills focused on the “answering” aspect over a 30-minute period

Figure 4.8: Diagram of the “responding” aspect

Based on the observation results regarding cooperation among group members over a 30-minute period, it can be seen that students’ ability to collaborate and build interactions with their peers within the same group falls into various categories. Jonathan Chrisea achieved the highest percentage—100%—in the “very active” category, indicating that he was highly consistent in maintaining communication, assisting other members, and fostering group cohesion throughout the discussion process. Meanwhile, Handhika Putra P and Helmy Achmad each achieved a score of 80%, falling into the “active” category.

Based on the observation results regarding the “responding” aspect over a 30-minute period, it is evident that students’ abilities to provide answers or respond to questions during discussions showed varying levels of activity. Wisnu and Zaul achieved the highest percentage—100%—in the “very active” category, indicating that they were highly consistent in answering questions, responding to discussions, and helping the group clarify the material. In addition, Ahmad Fais also demonstrated a high level of participation with a percentage of 71.42% and was classified as “very active.”

Group 2

a. Results by Indicator

1. Collaboration skills focused on the aspect of asking questions for 30 minutes

Figure 4.7: Diagram of the “asking questions” aspect

Based on the results of the observation of collaboration skills in the aspect of asking questions for 30 minutes, it is evident that the level of student engagement in asking questions shows a fairly clear difference. Wisnu Adi achieved the highest percentage—100%—in the “very active” category, indicating that he was the most consistent. Next, Khoirina Nisa was also in the “very active” category with a percentage of 87.55%, indicating that she asked questions quite frequently and demonstrated a high level of curiosity in participating in group activities.

3. Collaboration skills focused on active participation for 30 minutes

Figure 4.9: Diagram of active participation aspects

Based on the results of observations regarding active participation over a 30-minute period, it is evident that students’ engagement in group discussion activities showed varying levels of activity. Khoirina Nisa achieved the highest percentage—100%—falling into the “very active” category, indicating that she was the most consistent participant. Additionally, Ahmad Fais also fell into the “very active” category with a percentage of 88.88%.

4. Collaboration Skills Focused on the Aspect of Cooperation Over a 30-Minute Period

Figure 4.10: Diagram of the “Working Together” aspect

“Observing and Analyzing Collaboration Skills Through the STAD (Student Teams Achievement Division) Cooperative Learning Model”

Based on the observation results regarding the aspect of working together for 30 minutes, it is evident that students’ ability to collaborate in groups showed quite varied differences. Ahmad Fais and Wisnu Adi achieved the highest percentage—100%—in the “very active” category, indicating that both were very consistent in helping the group; Khoirina Nisa was also in the “very active” category with a percentage of 83.33%.

5. Collaboration skills focused on the aspect of contributing ideas over a 30-minute period.

Figure 4.11: Diagram of the “contributing ideas” aspect

Based on the observation results regarding the “generating ideas” aspect over 30 minutes, it is evident that students’ ability to convey ideas or suggestions during group discussions showed varying levels of activity. Laura Agustina achieved the highest percentage—100%—in the “very active” category, indicating that she was highly dominant in presenting ideas, offering suggestions, and assisting the group.

6. Collaboration skills focused on the aspect of cooperation among members for 30 minutes.

Figure 4.12: Diagram of the “Cooperation Among Members” aspect

7.

Based on the results of observations regarding cooperation among group members over a 30-minute period, it can be seen that students’ abilities to build interactions and cooperation with their groupmates showed varying levels of engagement. Zaul Kautsar received the highest percentage—100%—in the “very active” category, indicating that he was very consistent in establishing communication.

Group 3

a. Calculation Results by Indicator

1. Collaboration skills focused on the aspect of asking questions over a 30-minute period.

Figure 4.13: Diagram of the “asking questions” aspect

Based on the results of a 30-minute observation of collaboration skills in the area of asking questions, Rian and Nando achieved the highest percentage of 100% and were categorized as “very active.” Akbar and Davi achieved a percentage of 71.42% and were categorized as “active,” while Rika achieved a percentage of 14.28% and was categorized as “less active.”

2. For the “answering” aspect over a 30-minute period

Figure 4.14: Diagram of the “answering” aspect

Based on the results of the 30-minute observation of collaboration skills in the “answering” aspect, Rian and Rika achieved the highest percentage of 100%, falling into the “very active” category. Davi also fell into the “very active” category with a percentage of 85.71%. Meanwhile, Akbar achieved a percentage of 71.42% in the “active” category, and Nando achieved a percentage of 57.14% in the “fairly active” category.

3. Collaboration skills focused on the aspect of active participation over a 30-minute period

Figure 4.15: Diagram of active participation aspects

“Observing and Analyzing Collaboration Skills Through the STAD (Student Teams Achievement Division) Cooperative Learning Model”

Based on the observation results regarding active participation over a 30-minute period, it is evident that students’ engagement in group discussion activities showed varying levels of activity. Nanda achieved the highest percentage—100%—in the “very active” category, indicating that she was the most consistent participant.

4. Collaboration skills focused on the aspect of cooperation for 30 minutes

Figure 4.16: Diagram of the cooperation aspect

Based on the results of observations on the cooperation aspect over a 30-minute period, it is evident that students’ ability to collaborate within groups showed considerable variation. Akbar achieved the highest percentage—100%—in the “very active” category, indicating that he was very consistent in helping the group.

5. Collaboration skills focused on the aspect of contributing ideas for 30 minutes

Figure 4.17: Diagram of the “generating ideas” aspect

Based on the results of observations on the “idea generation” aspect over 30 minutes, it is evident that students’ abilities to convey ideas or suggestions during group discussions showed varying levels of activity. Rian achieved the highest percentage—100%—in the “very active” category, indicating that he was highly dominant in presenting ideas, offering suggestions, and assisting the group

6. Collaboration skills focused on the aspect of cooperation among members for 30 minutes

Figure 4.18: Diagram of the “Cooperation Among Members” aspect

Based on the results of observations regarding cooperation among group members over a 30-minute period, it can be seen that students’ ability to build interactions and cooperation with their groupmates showed varying levels of engagement. Rika received the highest percentage—100%—in the “very active” category, indicating that she was very consistent in establishing communication

Group 4

a. Calculation Results by Indicator

1. Collaboration skills focused on the “asking questions” aspect over 30 minutes

Figure 4.19: Diagram of the “asking questions” aspect

Based on the results of the observation of collaboration skills in the aspect of asking questions over a 30-minute period, Selandri achieved the highest percentage of 83.33%, falling into the “very active” category.

2. Collaboration skills focused on the “answering” aspect for 30 minutes

Figure 4.20: Diagram of the answering aspect

“Observing and Analyzing Collaboration Skills Through the STAD (Student Teams Achievement Division) Cooperative Learning Model”

Based on the results of the 30-minute observation of collaboration skills in the answering aspect, Rian and Rika achieved the highest percentage of 100% in the “very active” category.

3. Collaborative skills focused on the aspect of active participation for 30 minutes

Figure 4.21: Diagram of the active participation aspect

Based on the results of the 30-minute observation of active participation, it was evident that students’ engagement in group discussions varied in terms of activity levels. Rahma achieved the highest percentage—100%—in the “very active” category, indicating that she was the most consistent participant.

4. Collaboration skills focused on the aspect of working together for 30 minutes

Figure 4.22: Diagram of the cooperation aspect

Based on the results of observations on the cooperation aspect over a 30-minute period, it is evident that students’ ability to collaborate within groups showed quite varied levels. Selandri achieved the highest percentage—100%—in the “very active” category, indicating that she was very consistent in helping the group.

5. Collaboration skills focused on the aspect of contributing ideas for 30 minutes

Figure 4.23: Diagram of the “generating ideas” aspect.

Based on the results of observations on the “idea generation” aspect over 30 minutes, it is evident that students’ abilities to convey ideas or suggestions during group discussions showed varying levels of activity. Roni achieved the highest percentage—100%—in the “very active” category, indicating that he was highly dominant in presenting ideas, offering suggestions, and assisting the group.

6. Collaboration skills focused on the aspect of cooperation among members for 30 minutes

Figure 4.24: Diagram of the “Cooperation Among Members” aspect

Based on the results of the observation of cooperation among group members over a 30-minute period, it can be seen that students’ ability to build interactions and cooperation with their groupmates showed varying levels of engagement. Roni received the highest percentage—100%—in the “very active” category, indicating that he was very consistent in establishing communication with

Based on the results of the analysis of students’ collaboration skill observation scores listed in Table 4.1, the implementation of the *Student Teams Achievement Division* (STAD) learning model showed that students’ collaboration skill levels in mathematics learning fell into the “category”. All learning groups achieved a percentage of collaboration skills ranging from 66.75% to 76.05%, with an average percentage of 70.58% for the class, falling into the “active” category.

Table 4.1 Results of the Application of Students’ Collaboration Skills by Group

Group	Percentage	Category
1	76.05%	Active
2	66.75%	Active
3	69.67%	Active
4	69.86%	Active
Total	70.58%	Active

Based on the data presented in Table 4.2 below, the results of the observation of students’ collaboration skills after the implementation of the *Student Teams Achievement Division* (STAD) learning model indicate that there are several aspects of collaboration skills that demonstrate the highest level of collaboration in mathematics learning. These developed aspects include cooperation among group members and students’ active participation in learning activities, both of

“Observing and Analyzing Collaboration Skills Through the STAD (Student Teams Achievement Division) Cooperative Learning Model”

which fall under the “active” category. This indicates that the STAD cooperative learning model is effective in encouraging students to participate and cooperate with one another within their groups during the mathematics learning process. Meanwhile, the indicator with the lowest percentage was “contributing ideas,” with an average percentage of 67.01%, which also falls under the “active” category.

Table 4.2 Highest-Scoring Aspects of Collaborative Skills

Aspect	Grou p 1	Grou p 2	Grou p 3	Grou p 4	Total
Questions	66.66 %	67.55 %	71.42 %	75.00 %	70.00 %
Answer	78.12 %	71.42 %	82.85 %	57.55 %	72.48 %
Participati on	89.28 %	60.00 %	65.71 %	75.99 %	72.74 %
Collaborat e	71.42 %	76.66 %	60.00 %	66.66 %	68.68 %
Idea	70.83 %	55.55 %	66.66 %	75.00 %	67.01 %
Cooperati on among members	80.00 %	70.00 %	71.42 %	70.00 %	72.85 %

IV. DISCUSSION

This study employs a quantitative approach using a descriptive research design. The selection of this approach and research type was based on the research objectives, namely to obtain an overview of the level of implementation of the *Student Teams Achievement Division* (STAD) learning model in improving students' collaboration skills in mathematics learning, as well as to identify the aspects of collaboration skills that develop through the application of the STAD learning model in mathematics learning (Imda & Saefudin, 2025). Based on the observation results, Group 1 achieved a 76.05% agreement rate, which falls into the “active” category. This achievement indicates that most group members were able to demonstrate excellent collaboration skills, as reflected in strong cooperation, effective communication, and student engagement in group discussions. Meanwhile, Group 2, Group 3, and Group 4 achieved agreement percentages of 66.75%, 66.67%, and 69.86%, respectively, all falling within the “active” category. These results indicate that although the students' level of collaboration was not yet fully optimal, they were able to work together quite well, divide tasks proportionally, and participate in the process of solving math problems.

Furthermore, the aspects that showed improvement included students' active participation and their ability to collaborate with group members. The active participation aspect achieved a score of 72.74%, which falls into the “active” category. This result indicates that the implementation of the STAD model was able to increase student engagement in

learning activities. During the learning process, students were more engaged in group discussions, paid attention to their peers' explanations, and played an active role in completing assigned tasks. Meanwhile, the aspect of cooperation among group members achieved a percentage of 72.85%, also falling into the “active” category. These results show that students were able to build effective cooperation within their learning groups. Through the implementation of the STAD model, students were encouraged to help one another and share responsibility for the group's work, thereby fostering positive interactions among group members in solving mathematics problems.

This study is relevant to research conducted by Afifah Indar Febriyanti, Suhartono, and Kartika Chrysti Suryandari (2025), titled “Improving Collaboration Skills and Numeracy Abilities Through the Application of the Student Team Achievement Divisions (STAD) Model Among Second-Grade Students at . The results of this study are as follows: (1) the steps for implementing the STAD learning model are group formation, task assignment, administering quizzes or questions, evaluation, conclusion, and awarding recognition; (2) improved collaboration skills, as evidenced by the percentage of observation results in Cycle I = 78.33%, Cycle II = 87.49%, and Cycle III = 90.02%; (3) improved numeracy skills, as evidenced by the percentage of observation results in Cycle I = 76.38%, Cycle II = 87.50%, and Cycle III = 91.67%, as well as written test results in Cycle I = 73.13%, Cycle II = 84.34%, and Cycle III = 89.03%. The conclusion of this study is that students' collaboration skills have improved because they are now able to contribute actively, work productively, interact and communicate effectively, and use their time efficiently. Meanwhile, students' numeracy skills have also improved because they are now able to solve everyday problems involving symbols and numbers, and they are also able to interpret the results of their analysis to draw conclusions

V. CONCLUSION

The research results show that all learning groups achieved the “active” category with a relatively high level of collaboration skill attainment. Groups in the “active” category demonstrated strong cooperation, effective communication, and high student participation in group discussions. In general, the implementation of the STAD learning model was able to create a conducive and collaborative learning environment and increase student engagement in group work. Thus, the STAD learning model is worthy of being considered as an effective learning alternative for developing students' collaboration skills in mathematics learning. Furthermore, based on the highest-scoring aspects of the *Student Teams Achievement Division* (STAD) learning model, it has been proven to enhance students' collaboration skills in mathematics learning. Improvements were observed in the aspects of active participation, cooperation among members, the ability to

“Observing and Analyzing Collaboration Skills Through the STAD (Student Teams Achievement Division) Cooperative Learning Model”

express ideas, and cooperation among group members, all of which fell into the “active” category. This indicates that the STAD model is effective in encouraging student engagement, strengthening positive interactions, and fostering collaborative learning.

REFERENCES

1. Abdurahman, A., Wiliyanti, V., & Tarrapa, S. (2024). *21st-Century Learning Models*. PT. Sonpedia Publishing Indonesia.
2. Aje, A. U. (2022). *Cooperative Learning Models: Student Achievement Division (STAD) & Team Games Tournament (TGT)*. CV. Azka Pustaka.
3. Arum, D. S., & Hanif, M. (2025). Learning Strategies to Strengthen Motivation for Improving Students' Academic Achievement. *JPGENUS: Journal of Nusantara Generation Education*, 3(1), 37–47.
4. Darmawan, D., Sudrajat, I., Maulana, M. K. Z., & Febriyanto, B. (2021). Planning data collection to identify training needs at training institutions. *Journal of Nonformal Education and Community Empowerment*, 71–88.
5. Febriyanti, A. I., Suhartono, S., & Suryandari, K. C. (2025). Improving Collaboration Skills and Numeracy Abilities Through the Application of the Student Team Achievement Divisions (STAD) Model for Second-Grade Elementary School Students. *Kalam Cendekia: Scientific Journal of Education*, 13(1).
6. Ichiana, N. N., Razzaq, A., & Ahmad, A. K. (2023). The Merdeka Curriculum Orientation: Barriers to *Journal of Science Education*, 13(4), 1162–1173.
7. Ikhsan, M. M., & Sa'adah, N. (2024). The Effect of the STAD Cooperative Learning Model on Students' Mathematics Learning Outcomes. *Discovery: Journal of Science*, 9(2), 85–94.
8. Imda, N. N., & Saefudin, A. (2025). Application of the Student Teams Achievement Divisions (STAD) Learning Model in Developing Students' Attitudes Toward Cooperation and Creativity in Islamic Religious Education and Ethics Classes in Grade 5 at SD Negeri 3 Bulungan. *Action Research Journal Indonesia (ARJI)*, 7(4), 2510–2527.
9. LIA, A. C. S. (2021). *THE EFFECT OF COMBINING THE FLIP PEER INSTRUCTION LEARNING MODEL WITH STAD ON STUDENTS' CRITICAL THINKING SKILLS*. UIN RADEN INTAN LAMPUNG.
10. Liu, A. P., Lawe, Y. U., Pare, P. Y. D., & Dinatha, N. M. (2025). The Application of the STAD Cooperative Learning Model to Improve Student Learning Outcomes in Grade 5 Science at UPTD SDI Kolokoa. *Journal of Science Education*, 15(2), 680–685.
11. Margalita, C., Hamengkubuwono, H., & Arsil, A. (2025). *The Effect of the STAD Cooperative Learning Model on Students' Motivation in Akidah Akhlak Lessons at Ma Muhammadiyah Curup*. Curup State Islamic Institute.
12. MARIYAM, S. (2024). *DEVELOPMENT OF PROJECT-BASED LEARNING STUDENT ACTIVITY SHEETS TO ENHANCE COLLABORATIVE SKILLS AND CREATIVITY AMONG EIGHTH-GRADE STUDENTS AT TULANG BAWANG BARAT STATE JUNIOR HIGH SCHOOL 5*. Muhammadiyah University of Metro.
13. Mubarak, R. (2021). Development of human resource management in Islamic educational institutions. *AL-FAHIM: Journal of Islamic Education Management*, 3(2), 131–146.
14. Nirfayanti, N., & Syamsuriyawati, S. (2024). Development of Active, Collaborative, and Inductive Cooperative Learning Models to Improve Junior High School Students' Mathematical Generalization Skills. *De Fermat: Journal of Mathematics Education*, 7(1), 46–60.
15. Noperman, F. (2022). *LEARNING INNOVATION: From Creative Ideas in the Mind to Innovative Practices in the Classroom*. Laksbang Pustaka.
16. Nurhayati, S., Septikasari, D., Judijanto, L., Susanto, D., Sudadi, S., Setiyana, R., Willdahlia, A. G., Ramli, A., & Zamroni, Z. (2025). *A New Paradigm in 21st-Century Education*. PT. Green Pustaka Indonesia.
17. Pare, A., & Sihotang, H. (2023). Holistic education to develop 21st-century skills in facing the challenges of the digital age. *Tambusai Education Journal*, 7(3), 27778.
18. Suryo Widodo, J., Santia, I., & Katminingsih, Y. (2019). *Journal of Math Educator Nusantara (JMEN)*.
19. Vivando, A., Purnawirawan, O., & Zulvarina, P. (2026). The Effect of the STAD Cooperative Learning Model Assisted by Wordwall on Improving Student Learning Outcomes and Collaboration. *Journal of Information Technology and Computer Science Development*, 10(4).
20. Wahyudi, W. (2024). Implementation of the Teams Games Tournament to Improve Collaboration Skills Among Elementary School Students. *Scholaria: Journal of Education and Culture*, 14(01), 88–97.
21. ZISPITA, W. (2025). *THE EFFECT OF A PEER-REVIEW-ASSISTED COLLABORATIVE LEARNING MODEL ON STUDENTS' SHORT STORY WRITING SKILLS IN THE INDONESIAN LANGUAGE COURSE FOR FIFTH GRADE AT MI AULIA CENDEKIA IN PEKANBARU*. SULTAN SYARIF KASIM RIAU STATE ISLAMIC UNIVERSITY.